

**DSA ERI STANDARD. ELECTRONIC DIGITAL SIGNATURE OF GOST
R 34.10-94**

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ANNOTATION

In this article, the concepts of electronic digital signature and the main goals of its use are shown. In addition, the science "Cryptography", which is the basis of electronic signature, and the initial encryption algorithms of this science are given, examples of them are shown. An electronic digital signature based on DSA and GOST R 34.10-94 encryption algorithm is described.

Key words : encryption , DES, **GOST R 34.10-94**

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Key words: encryption, RSA, El-Gamal, Cryptography

Enter

In 1991, the draft of the DSS (Digital Signature Standard) ERI standard based on the DSA (Digital Signature Algorithm) algorithm was discussed by NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology). This algorithm is based on the complexity of the discrete logarithmization problem in a finite field with a sufficiently large fundamental characteristic whose tolerance is given below is a sequence of algorithm steps.

Creating a signature

1. The sender of information publicly announces *the M -data and the following parameters to a wide range of system users:*

p is a prime number, $2^{512} < p < 2^{1024}$, the bit length is a multiple of 64;

q is a prime number, $2^{159} < q < 2^{160}$, the divisor of $p-1$;

$g = h^{(p-1)/q} \bmod p$, where h is an integer satisfying the conditions $0 < h < p$ and $h^{(p-1)/q} \bmod p > 1$;

y is a public key defined by the formula $y = g^x \text{ mod } p$. Here x is a secret key taken from the range $0 < x < q$ and known only to the signer;

$H(M)$ is a hash function that generates an integer in the interval $[1; q]$ from M data.

2. The data sender chooses a random number k from the interval $0 < k < q$, keeps it secret and loses it immediately after signature generation.

3. The data sender calculates r and s values using the following law:

$$r = g^k \text{ mod } p \text{ mod } q$$

$$s = k^{-1} (xr + H(M)) \text{ mod } q.$$

M is the signature on the data (r, s) consists of a pair of numbers.

Signature verification. Receiver M' data and (r', s') accepts the signature. He should check whether the data M and M' match. To do this, he performs the following sequence of steps:

1. $0 < s' < q$ or $0 < r' < q$ is not met, the signature is considered a forgery and signature verification is terminated.

2. $v = (s')^{-1} \text{ mod } q$ is found.

3. $z_1 = H(M') v \text{ mod } q, z_2 = r' v \text{ mod } q$.

4. Then $u = g^{z_1} y^{z_2} \text{ mod } p \text{ mod } q$.

5. If the equality $r' = u$ holds, then the signature is valid and the equality $M = M'$ is true.

Correctness of the algorithm. Let $M = M', s' = s$, and $r' = r$. Then it is shown that the equality $r = u$ holds.

So, since $v = (s')^{-1} \text{ mod } q, z_1 = H(M') v \text{ mod } q, z_2 = r' v \text{ mod } q$, the following can be written:

$$u = g^{z_1} y^{z_2} \text{ mod } p \text{ mod } q = g^{H(M)s^{-1}} g^{xrs^{-1}} \text{ mod } p \text{ mod } q =$$

$$= g^{k(xr + H(M))^{-1} (xr + H(M))} \text{ mod } p \text{ mod } q = g^k \text{ mod } p \text{ mod } q = r.$$

It can be seen that the equality $r = u$ is valid. Thus, the correctness of the algorithm was proved.

Electronic digital signature of GOST R 34.10-94

It was considered the Russian standard until 2000 GOST R 34.10-94 ERI algorithm is considered. This algorithm is similar to the DSA algorithm and uses the following initial open parameters:

1) L A large p prime number is selected with length L , where L the number is selected from the range of 509 bits to 512 bits or 1020 bits to 1024 bits, that is, $2^{509} < p < 2^{512}$ or $2^{1020} < p < 2^{1024}$.

2) L_1 A large q prime number of length L_1 is chosen, where L_1 the number is chosen from 254 bits to 256 bits, that is $2^{254} < p < 2^{256}$, .

3) a number $g^q \bmod p = 1$ in the interval g satisfying the condition $0 < g < p - 1$ is selected.

4) $y = g^x \bmod p$ from y - is the public key, where $0 < x < q$ is the secret key obtained from the interval .

5) $H(M)$ - the hash-function is given M - is an integer calculated on the data and accepts values in the range from $1 < H(M) < q$ to , i.e. q .

Signature generation algorithm. Initial data: M - data, given parameters and secret key. Result: signature - (r, s) .

1) a $1 \leq k \leq q$ random k number is taken from the interval, it is kept secret and is lost immediately after signing.

2) $r = (g^k \bmod p) \bmod q$ is considered.

3) M The hash value of the information being sent is calculated.
 $e := H(M)$

4) If $r = 0$ or $H(M) \bmod q = 0$, then go to step 1 and k choose another.

5) $s = (xr + kH(M)) \bmod q$, where the secret key x is known only to the signer.

6) If $s = 0$ yes, then go to step 1.

7) M information signature - (r, s) consists of a pair.

Signature verification algorithm. Initial data: M data, given parameters, signature verification key and M data signature. Result: Confirmation of signature authenticity or forgery.

1) If $1 \leq r, s \leq q - 1$ the condition is not met, then the signature forgery and the signature verification algorithm are terminated. If these conditions are met, the next step will be taken.

2) $e := h(m)$ is considered

3) $w := H(M)^{(q-2)} \bmod q$ is considered

4) $u_1 := sw \bmod q$ is considered

5) $u_2 := (q - r)w \bmod q$ is considered

6) $u := (g^{u_1} y^{u_2} \bmod p) \bmod q$ is considered

7) If $u = r$ the condition is met, then the signature is valid, otherwise the signature is forged and the signature verification algorithm is terminated.

Correctness of the signature algorithm of GOST R 34.10-94. We need to show that the value of the r parameter obtained from the GOST R 34.10-94 digital signature generation algorithm is equal to the value of the u parameter in the signature verification algorithm .

Indeed, $u = (g^{u_1} y^{u_2} \bmod p) \bmod q = g^{sw \bmod q} \cdot g^{x(q-r)w \bmod q} \bmod p \bmod q =$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= g^{(s+xq-xr)w \bmod q} \bmod p \bmod q = g^{(xr+kH(M)+xq-xr)w \bmod q} \bmod p \bmod q = \\
 &= g^{(kH(M)+xq)w \bmod q} \bmod p \bmod q = \\
 &= g^{kH(M)w \bmod q} \bmod p \cdot (g^q \bmod p)^{xw \bmod q} \bmod q = \\
 &= / (g^q \bmod p) = 1 \text{ according to the condition, } (g^q \bmod p)^{xw \bmod q} \bmod q \\
 &= 1 \text{ equality holds } / = \\
 &= g^{kH(M)w \bmod q} \bmod p \bmod q = / w = H(M)^{(q-2)} \bmod q, \text{ according to the} \\
 &\text{condition } 0 < H(M) < q \text{ (} q \text{ - prime) and the Euler-Fermat theorem } H(M)^{(q-2)} \\
 &\bmod q = H(M)^{-1} \text{ it follows that the degree of } g \text{ can be expressed as } kH(M)w = kH \\
 &(M)H(M)^{q-2} \bmod q = kH(M)H(M)^{-1} = k / = g^k \bmod p \bmod q = r. \text{ Thus the} \\
 &\text{required condition was shown.}
 \end{aligned}$$

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